

FORMULATION DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF BILAYER TABLET CONTAINING DESVENLAFAXINE SUCCINATE SUSTAINED RELEASE AND CLONAZEPAM IMMEDIATE RELEASE DRUGS

Praveen Tiwari *¹, Ankur Bharadhwaj², Phool Singh Yaduwanshi³, Kavita R Loksh⁴,
Gaurav Jain⁵

IES Institute of Pharmacy, IES University, Bhopal (Madhya Pradesh)

Corresponding author : Praveen Tiwari

Received: Jun 15, 2025

Accepted: July 17, 2025

Published: July 21, 2025

ABSTRACT

The aim of the present research was to develop a bilayer tablet of containing Desvenlafaxine succinate sustained release and Clonazepam immediate release drugs. The sustained and immediate layer tablet were prepared by wet granulation method, they were evaluated for weight variation, drug content, friability, hardness, and thickness for all batches D1-D8 and C1-C7. The drug excipient compatibility was done at accelerated temperature 40°C/75%RH±5% and 30°C/60%RH +5% relative humidity. Among different trials with wet granulation, trial D8 for Desvenlafaxine SR part & trial C6 for clonazepam IR part showed satisfactory *in vitro* dissolution profile so these two were selected for the preparation of bilayer tablets. Results of stability studies of batch DC8:(D8+C6) Indicates that it was stable at 40°C/75% RH ± 5% relative humidity as there was no significant difference was observed for dissolution and average drug content data after 3 months. From the Bilayer tablets batch number DC8:D8+C6 found satisfactory *in vitro* dissolution profile with their respective innovators. Opened and closed vial methods were used. The result does not show any physical change to the mixture after 30 days. This fact concluded that the drug and excipient are compatible with each other. The data of uniformity of content indicated that tablets of all batches had drug content within pharmacopoeia limits. The hardness of tablets of all batches is in acceptable limits, as shown in the literature. All the formulation showed % friability less than 1% that indicates ability of tablets to withstand shocks, which may encounter.

Keywords: Desvenlafaxine succinate, Clonazepam, Bilayer tablets, *in vitro* dissolution.

1. INTRODUCTION

Tablets are the most popular oral formulations available in the market and preferred by the patients and physicians alike. Sustained release tablet formulations are much desirable and preferred for such therapy because they offer better patient compliance, maintain uniform drug levels, reduce dose and side effects, and increase safety margin for high-potency drugs (Andrade, 2015). The term bilayered tablets containing subunits that may be either the same (homogeneous: one layer of drug for immediate release while second layer for extended release) or different (heterogeneous: sequential release of two drugs in combination or separate two incompatible substances) (Kiran *et al.*, 2015).

DSV, being a weak basic drug, dissolves easily in gastric fluids and is highly absorbed after oral administration, which exaggerates its side effects. Indeed, this highlights the need to prepare extended release of DSV tablets to increase the compliance of patients suffering from depressive disorder and decrease side effects compared to the immediate release formulation (Franek *et al.*, 2015). SNRIs act upon and increase the levels of two neurotransmitters in the

brain that are known to play an important part in mood, these being serotonin and norepinephrine. This can be contrasted with the more widely-used selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) which act more selectively on serotonin (Olivier, 2015).

Clonazepam (CLZ) is a benzodiazepine anticonvulsant drug, which is commonly indicated for seizure, panic, epilepsy, and anxiety disorders. CLZ has a limited dissolution, as well as poor absorption and distribution profiles (Brigo and Lattanzi 2022). Clonazepam (CLZ) is a benzodiazepine anticonvulsant drug, which is commonly indicated for seizure, panic, epilepsy, and anxiety disorders. CLZ has a limited dissolution, as well as poor absorption and distribution profiles. The use of hydrophilic polymers, such as hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose (HPMC) or different grades of polyethylene glycols (PEG), is valuable for improving CLZ solubility by the formulation of a solid dispersion and consequently positively affects its therapeutic efficacy (Mahmood *et al.*, 2023).

The aim of the present study was to formulation and evaluate of Bilayer tablet containing Desvenlafaxine succinate sustained release and Clonazepam immediate release drugs.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Chemicals

Clonazepam for IR part were produced from Cadila Pharmaceutical Ltd., Ahmedabad, India, a well-known provider of high-quality laboratory chemicals. Desvenlafaxine Succinate USP for SR part was obtained from Ami LifeScienceLtd, Baroda, India, while Microcrystalline cellulose (Avicel pH102 and 200) was supplied by FMC BioPolymer, Philadelphia, U.S. Lactose monohydrate was purchased from Dynamix Dairy Industry, Mumbai, India. Additionally, Maize Starch were sourced from DMV International, Veghel, Netherlands. Starch, Pregelatinized was acquired from Colorcon, WestPoint, PA, US.

2.2 Pre-formulation study

Pre-formulation can be defined as investigation of physical and chemical properties of drug substance alone and when combined with excipients. Pre-formulation studies are the first step in the rational development of dosage form of a drug substance. The objectives of pre-formulation studies are to development of information about the drug substance, so that this information is useful to develop formulation.

2.2.1 Drug identification by FTIR

Method: Triturate sufficient to grate 1-2 mg of the substance to be examined with 300-400 mg unless otherwise specified, of finely powdered and dried potassium bromide or potassium chloride. These quantities are usually sufficient to give a disc of 10-15 mm diameter and a spectrum of suitable intensity. Infrared spectrophotometers are for recording spectra in the region of 4000-650.

2.2.2 Solubility Study

The solubility of Desvenlafaxine succinate and Clonazepam was determined by dissolving the drug in mg per ml of the solvents (Breda *et al.* 2009)

2.2.3 Drug-Excipient and Drug-Drug compatible study

Calculate Drug: Excipients ratio for each excipient to be used. Decide approximate concentration of excipients on slightly higher side on the basis of Drug: Excipient ratio. About 10 mg of Drug is required for analysis and as per concentration decided for (Ex. Drug: MCC ratio is 1: 10) Take 10 mg of Drug and 100 mg of MCC in vial. Fill up all the vials with

same procedure. Study is carried out for 6 conditions, so quantity of drug will be 60 mg and 600 mg for MCC and total blend will be of 660 mg to be placed in vial. Follow same procedure in case of excipients used alone. Label all the vials with condition mentioned in table and load in humidity chambers after the time period mentioned in days check out the compatibility by Physical appearance (Savva, 2019).

Acceptance criteria: Single maximum unknown impurities not more than 0.2 % and total impurities not more than 2.0%.

2.3 Formulation development

2.3.1 Manufacturing procedure of SR Tablet of Desvenlafaxine Succinate:

- **Wet granulation Method:**

1. Weight accurately Desvenlafaxine succinate, Lactose monohydrate, HPMC KM, MCC 200 and Talc pass through sieve 40 # Meshes and mix properly for 3 to 5 minutes in a steel tub.
2. Prepare Binder solution by dispersing PVPK-30 in Water.
3. Granulation of above mixture is done by prepared binder solution by kneading up to granulation end point is obtained (Dough mass). Pass the Dough mass through the sieve 12 # Meshes and keep it in a tray dryer for drying and finally keep the loss of drying (LOD) up to 2 to 3%. Remove the dried granules from oven and pass through 20 # Meshes sieve to get optimum size of granules. Add extra granular part pass through the 30 # Mesh sieve and add while lubrication.
4. Lubrication is done by using Mg. stearate and passes through 60 # Mesh sieve of granules for 3 to 4 minutes in a steel tub and then in poly beg.
5. Compression is done by using 16 station single rotary CADMACH machine by using 9.6 mm round, biconcave, both side plane punch.

- **Design and Development of Desvenlafaxine Succinate SR Tablet**

Table 1:- Formulation of Batch D1-D8

Formulation ingredients	TRIAL BATCHES							
	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6	D7	D8
Desvenlafaxine succinate	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Lactose monohydrate	105	90	82	78	77	71.5	72	72
HPMC K4M	40	50	55	55	55	55	55	53
MCC 200	20	22	25	25	25	25	25	27
Talc	5	5	5	5	3	3	2.5	2.5
PVPK30	7	5	5	4	4	4	4	4
Water	qs	qs	qs	qs	qs	qs	qs	qs
HPMC K4M	100	100	100	100	100	105	105	105
MCC 200	30	35	35	40	42	42	42	42
Talc	1	1	1	1	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Mg.stearate	2	2	2	2	2.5	3	3	3
Total weight	410	410	410	410	410	410	410	410

2.3.2 Manufacturing procedure of IR Tablet of Clonazepam

- **Wet granulation Method:**

1. Weight accurately Clonazepam, Lactose monohydrate, Maize starch, and Pregelatinised starch pass through sieve 40 # Meshes and mix properly for 3 to 5 minutes in a steel tub.

2. Solution for granulation is Water.
3. Granulation of above mixture is done by prepared binder solution by kneeding up to granulation end point is obtained (Dough mass). Pass the Dough mass through the sieve 12 # Meshes and keep it n a tray dryer for drying and finally keep the loss of drying(LOD) up to 2 to 3%. Remove the dried granules from oven and pass through 20 # Meshes sieve to get optimum size of granules. Add extra granular part pass through the 30 # Mesh sieve and add while lubrication and Pass Iron oxide Redfrom sieve 90 Meshes.
4. Lubrication is done by using Mg. stearate and passes through 60 # Mesh sieve of granules for 3 to 4 minutes in a steel tub and then in poly beg.
5. Compression is done by using 16 station single rotary CADMACH machine by using 9.6 mm round, bio concave, both side plane punch.

• **Design and Development of Desvenlafaxine Succinate SR and Clonazepam IR Bilayer Tablet:**

Comparatively Batch number D6, D7 and D8 of Desvenlafaxine Succinate shows similarity dissolution release profile with innovator release profile. And Batch number C5, C6, and C7 batches of Clonazepam show somewhat dissolution release compare with innovator release profile.

Table 2:- Formulation of Batch DC1-DC9

Tablet ingredient (mg)	Desvenlafaxine succinate sustained release layer		Clonazepam immediate release layer	
	HPMC K4M(mg)	Starch 1500(mg)	Pregelatinised Starch (mg)	MCC Ph102(mg)
DC1(D6+C5)	121	33	6	40
DC2(D6+C6)	121	28	6	45
DC3:(D6+C7)	121	23	6	50
DC4:(D7+C5)	132	13	6	40
DC5:(D7+C6)	132	15	6	45
DC6:(D7+C7)	132	12	6	50
DC7:(D8+C5)	132	22	6	40
DC8:(D8+C6)	132	17	6	45
DC9:(D8+C7)	132	11	6	50

2.4 Evaluation studies

Evaluation of Granules of Desvenlafaxine Succinate and Clonazepam

2.4.1 Determination of bulk density and tapped density

Weigh accurately 25 g of drug (M), which was previously passed through 20 # sieve and transferred in 100 ml graduated cylinder. Carefully level the powder without compacting, and read the unsettled apparent volume (V_0). Calculate the apparent bulk density in gm/ml by the following formula

$$\text{Bulk density} = W/V_0$$

2.4.2 Tapped bulk density:

Weigh accurately 25 g of drug, which was previously passed through 20 # sieve and transfer in 100 ml graduated cylinder. Then mechanically tap the cylinder containing the sample by raising the cylinder and allowing it to drop under its own weight using mechanically tapped density tester that provides a fixed drop of 14 ± 2 mm at a nominal rate of 300 drops per

minute.

$$\text{Tapped density} = W/V_f$$

2.4.3 Loss of drying:

%L.O.D. of the compound measure the % content of water present in compound

2.4.4 Angle of repose

The angle of repose of API powder was determined by the fix funnel method

$$\tan \Theta = h/r$$

$$\Theta = \tan^{-1}(h/r)$$

Where, h =Height of pile, r = radius of the base of the pile, Θ = angle of repose

Table 3:- Effect of Angle of repose on Flow property

Angle of Repose	Type of Flow
<20	Excellent
20-30	Good
30-34	Passable
>35	Very poor

2.5 Standard curve of Desvenlafaxine succinate and Clonazepam

For Desvenlafaxine succinate and Clonazepam

100 mg equivalent of Desvenlafaxine succinate was dissolved in 100 ml of 0.9N NaCl and Clonazepam was dissolved in 100 ml of water. The 10 ml of Desvenlafaxine succinate solution was further diluted with 0.9N NaCl to get drug concentration 5, 10, 15, 20, 25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 10 ml of Clonazepam solution was further diluted with water to get drug concentration 4, 8, 12, 16, 20, 24, 28, 32 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ the absorbance of the solution was measured as a blank at nm using double beam UV visible spectrophotometer. The plot of absorbance v/s concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) was plotted and data was obtained linear regression analysis.

2.6 Dissolution Study

26.1 For Desvenlafaxine succinate and clonazepam

Procedure: Set dissolution apparatus with above parameters and add 900 mL of dissolution medium to each of six glass vessels and lower down the hood. Place 1 tablet in to each vessel taking care to exclude the air bubbles from the surface of the tablet and immediately start the apparatus. After 1, 4, 8, 16, 24 hours, withdraw 10 mL of the Desvenlafaxine succinate sample from the each of six glass vessels and filter immediately through 0.45 μ nylon filter. 5,10,15,30,45,60, withdraw 10 mL of the clonazepam sample from the each of six glass vessels and filter immediately through 0.45 μ nylon filter. Discard first few mL of filtrate (Sample preparation).

2.7 Evaluation of Devenlafaxine succinate tablet

- Weight variation: Twenty tablets were randomly selected from each batch and individually weighted. The average weight a standard deviation of 20 tablets was calculated (**Razavi et al., 2020**).
- Dimensions: Twenty tablets were randomly selected from each batch and there thickness and diameter was measured by using digital vernier caliper.
- Hardness test: Hardness was measured by using Monsanto hardness tester.

- Friability test: Twenty tablets were weighted and placed in the Elecrolab friabilator and apparatus was rotated at 25 rpm for 4 minutes (**Osei-Yeboah and Sun 2015**). The percentage friability was measured using formula,

$$\%F = \{1 - (W_t/W)\} \times 100$$

- Buffer preparation: Dissolve an accurately weighed quantity about 36.5 g of Sodium Chloride in 1000mL of water. Adjust to pH 6.50 (± 0.05) with diluted phosphoric acid. Filter the solution through 0.45 μ Nylon filters and degas before use (**Leshe, 2015**).
- Mobile phase: Prepared a mixture of 650 volumes of Buffer preparation and 350 Volumes of Acetonitrile.
- Standard preparation: Transfer an accurately weighed quantity about 99.5 mg of Desvenlafaxine working standard and 25.5 mg of Clonazepam working standard in to a 200 mL volumetric flask. Dissolve with 100 mL of diluent A and sonicate to dissolve. Cool and dilute to volume with water and mix. Dilute 5.0 mL of this solution to 50 mL with diluent B and mix (**Alasabashi, 2021**).
- Assay preparation: Weigh and powder 20 tablets. Transfer an accurately weighed Quantity of tablet powder equivalent to 100.0 mg of Desvenlafaxine and 0.5 mg of Clonazepam in to a 200mL volumetric flask. Add 100mL of diluent A and sonicate for 30 minutes. Dilute to volume with water and mix. Filter the solution with 0.45 μ Nylon filter. Discarded first few mL of filtrate. Dilute 5.0 mL of this Solution to 50 mL with diluent B and mix.

Procedure: Inject 20 μ L of the assay preparation (in duplicate) in to the liquid chromatograph and record the chromatograms. Measure the response for Desvenlafaxine and Clonazepam peak. Calculate the content of the Desvenlafaxine and Clonazepam in percentage from the mean peak area of the standard and assay preparation and the percentage of the potency used from the given formula.

Calculation: % of Desvenlafaxine

$$\frac{A_u}{A_s} \times \frac{W_1}{200} \times \frac{5}{50} \times \frac{200}{W_2} \times \frac{50}{5} \times \frac{W_3}{L.C} \times P$$

2.8 Stability study of Tablet F batch (DC8:D8+C6)

The batch (DC8:D8+C6) was selected as an optimum batch and the stability study was carried out at accelerated condition of 40C/75 %RH condition for a period of three months.

Method: Ten tablets were individually wrapped using aluminium foil and packed in cambered color screw cap bottle and put at above specified condition in incubator for 3 months. After three months tablets were evaluated for content uniformity and in-vitro drug release.

Observation: The results of stability study after 3 months are given in table The plot of cumulative % drug release v/s Time duplicated in graph.

Drug content: Comparative content uniformity of the tablet after 3months stability.

Table 7:- Drug-Excipient compatibility studies

Drug: Excipient (1:1)	Observation		
	Description	30°C/65%RH	50°C/80%RH
Clonazepam IP	White to off White powder	White to off White powder	White to off White powder
Desvenlafaxine	White to off White powder	White to off white powder	White to off White powder
Desvenlafaxine: Clonazepam	White to off white powder	White to off white powder	White to off white powder
Desvenlafaxine: Lactose Monohydrate	White to off yellow powder	White to off reddish powder	White to dark Reddish Brown powder
Desvenlafaxine: HPMC K4M	White to off White powder	White to off White powder	White to off White powder
Desvenlafaxine:PVPK-30	White to off White powder	White to off White powder	White to off White powder
Desvenlafaxine: Magnesium stearate	White to off white powder	White to off white powder	White to off white powder
Clonazepam: Lactose monohydrate	White to off white powder	White to off white powder	White to off white powder
Clonazepam: Pregelatinized Starch	White to off white powder	White to off white powder	White to off white powder
Clonazepam: MCC101	White to off White powder	White to off White powder	White to off White powder
Clonazepam: Maize Starch	White to off White powder	White to off White powder	White to off White powder
Clonazepam: Iron Oxide Red	Brick Red Colored Powder	Brick Red Colored Powder	Brick Red Colored Powder

3.2 Standard curve of Desvenlafaxine succinate and Clonazepam

Observation: the standard calibration curve of Desvenlafaxine succinate in 0.9N NaCL and Clonazepam in water replicated as figure. The data has correlation coefficient of Desvenlafaxine succinate of 0.992 and correlation coefficient of Clonazepam of 0.993.

3.3 Characterization

3.3.1 Characterization of trial batches for Clonazepam

Table 8:- Characterization of Batch C1-C8

Batch No.	% LOD	Angle of	Bulk Density(g/ml)	Tapped Density(g/ml)	Carr's Index(%)	Hausner Ratio
C1	2.13	25.33	0.56	0.65	13.85	1.16
C2	2.20	27.15	0.52	0.60	13.33	1.15
C3	2.15	26.42	0.53	0.59	10.17	1.11
C4	2.05	24.78	0.55	0.62	11..29	1.13

C5	2.10	25.89	0.54	0.63	14.29	1.17
C6	2.08	27.03	0.53	0.61	13.11	1.15
C7	2.05	27.25	0.55	0.60	14.01	1.16

3.3.2 Characterization of trial batches For Desvenlafaxine succinate

Table 9:- characterization of Batch D1-D8

Batch No.	% LOD	Angle of	Bulk Density(g/ml)	Tapped Density(g/ml)	Carr's Index	Hausner's Ratio
D1	1.98	28.50	0.57	0.63	9.52	1.11
D2	1.81	27.67	0.52	0.58	10.34	1.12
D3	1.15	29.35	0.59	0.68	13.24	1.15
D4	1.72	28.23	0.56	0.64	12.50	1.14
D5	1.68	25.13	0.48	0.53	9.43	1.10
D6	1.75	26.17	0.51	0.58	12.07	1.14
D7	1.53	28.33	0.54	0.61	11.48	1.13
D8	1.85	26.55	0.47	0.52	9.62	1.11

Table 10:- Characterization of Bilayer table

Trials	weight variation mg*	Thickness mm*	Hardness Kg/cm*	Friability %	Drug content Desvenlafaxine	Drug content Clonazepam
DC1:D6+C5	610±1.97	5.10±0.2	10	0.63±0.03	101.65	101.65
DC2:D6+C6	610±1.86	5.10±0.2	8	0.62±0.04	98.22	98.22
DC3:D6+C7	610±3.25	5.10±0.2	9	0.542±0.0	103.99	103.99
DC4:D7+C5	610±1.56	5.10±0.2	6	0.53±0.04	100.82	100.82
DC5:D7+C6	610±2.96	5.10±0.2	7	0.670±0.0	95.12	95.12
DC6:D7+C7	610±2.39	5.10±0.2	9	0.61±0.03	99.25	99.25
DC7:D8+C5	610±1.54	5.10±0.2	8	0.41±0.01	94.21	94.21
DC8:D8+C6	610±2.89	5.10±0.2	6	0.45±0.02	100.45	100.45
DC9:D8+C7	610±1.54	5.10±0.2	9	0.542±0.0	98.22	98.22

3.4 Stability study of Tablet F batch (DC8:D8+C6)

Table 11:- Drug content of batch (DC8:D8+C6) kept in stability

Desvenlafaxine succinate	
Time	Drug content (%)
Zero month	100.41
Three month	100.27
Clonazepam	
Time	Drug content (%)
Zero month	99.76
Three month	99.54

3.5 Dissolution Study

3.5.1 Dissolution profile of batch (DC8:D8+C6) Kept for stability of three months

Table 12:- For Desvenlafaxine succinate				Table 13:- For Clonazepam			
	Time in Hours	Cumulative% release		Dissolution Medium 900 mL Water	Time in Hours	Cumulative% release	
		Initial	3 Months			Initial	3 Months
	0.5	3.7	3.5		5	22.4	21.4
Dissolution Medium	1	12.5	11.2		10	49.8	46.5
900ml0.9N NaCL	2	22.1	20.1		15	67.4	65.8
	4	36.2	34.8		30	86.6	83.1
	6	43.5	41.4		45	93.7	92.9
	8	60.1	59.2		60	100.8	99.6
	12	72.9	71.6				
	16	81.9	80.8				
	20	92.4	91.6				
	24	101.4	100.2				

3.5.2 Dissolution profile of Desvenlafaxine succinate batch number D1toD8:

Table 14:- Dissolution profile of Desvenlafaxine succinate batch D1-D8

Time in Hours	CUMULATIVE % RELEASE							
	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6	D7	D8
0.5	0.3	1.1	1.4	2.8	6.2	1.8	3.3	3.9
1	0.8	5.6	6.1	8.5	18.7	6.4	12.4	13.2
2	1.4	9.3	10.1	16.2	25.1	14.3	23.8	22.1
4	2.5	15.5	16.2	23.1	35.3	24.4	36.3	34.6
6	4.4	24.4	25.3	28.8	47.2	38.1	47.8	48.9
8	5.3	28.5	29.1	33.4	60.4	47.5	61.3	63.2
12	10.1	30.3	35.4	46.2	69.9	60.8	71.2	72.4
16	11.8	44.6	42.3	58.3	78.7	75.7	85.8	87.1
20	18.3	48.2	48.9	66.3	85.6	90.3	91.8	92.3
24	23.3	54.1	59.3	80.1	90.1	97.5	98.9	101.9

Graph 5: Comparative Dissolution profile of Batch D1-D

3.5.3 Dissolution profile of Desvenlafaxine succinate batch number C1 to C7:

Table 15:- Dissolution profile of Clonazepam batch number C1-C7

Time in minutes	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7
5	5.8	6.9	10.3	39.8	20.6	20.4	22.4
10	13.5	17.8	22.9	62.4	47.5	46.8	49.8
15	31.3	44.2	50.6	81.8	64.3	65.4	67.4
30	50.4	61.3	65.4	91.4	80.9	81.6	86.6
45	61.3	70.5	87.4	96.3	93.5	92.7	93.7
60	66.7	79.8	96.8	99.2	98.7	99.1	100.8

Graph 6: Comparative Dissolution profile of batch C1-C7

3.5.4 Dissolution study of Desvenlafaxine succinate and Clonazepam Bilayer tablet

Table 16:- Dissolution of Desvenlafaxine succinate in Bilayer tablet

Time in Hours	Cumulative %Release										
	0.5	1	2	4	6	8	12	16	20	24	
DC1:D6+C5	D6	1.2	6.2	17	22.7	33	44.1	57	68.3	74.3	81.7
DC2:D6+C6		2.8	7.4	19	27.4	35	48.3	58	70.2	76.9	83.9
DC3:D6+C7		3.2	8.1	14	23.1	30	43.5	53	64.2	69.1	72.5
DC4:D7+C5	D7	2.9	19.1	27	39.1	48	59.2	66	75.2	85.9	94.2
DC5:D7+C6		2.1	16.3	27	37.4	43	61.4	69	77.1	86.2	96
DC6:D7+C7		3.1	18.2	28	41.2	46	64.1	71	79.9	87.1	99.2
DC7:D8+C5)	D8	4	14.2	21	37.1	45	62.1	75	85.2	90.1	98.1
DC8:D8+C6		3.7	12.5	22	36.2	44	60.1	73	81.9	92.4	101
DC9:D8+C7		4.1	11.3	25	37.4	46	62.5	74	84.1	93	99.5

Graph 7: Cumulative % release of Desvenlafaxine succinate in Bilayer tablet

Table 17:- Dissolution of Clonazepam in Bilayer tablet

Time in Hours	Cumulative %Release					
	5	10	15	30	45	60
DC1:D6+C5	28.1	41.2	59.9	71.1	83.7	93.1
DC2:D6+C6	21.1	37.5	55.3	67.8	79.1	92.4
DC3:D6+C7	18.2	31.1	49.7	62.1	72.4	91.8
DC4:D7+C5	27.1	39.8	61.4	73.2	82.8	95.7
DC5:D7+C6	24.3	40.2	55.3	64.2	79.2	89.2
DC6:D7+C7	27.9	43.6	52.1	67.1	73.1	91.8
DC7:D8+C5)	20.1	40.2	64.2	77.9	88.1	96.3
DC8:D8+C6	24.1	46.5	67.2	88.1	92.3	99.7
DC9:D8+C7	19.1	41.2	59.2	73.5	84.1	87.4

Graph 8: Cumulative % release of Clonazepam batch of DC1toDC9

3.6 Design and Development of Clonazepam IR Tablet:

Table 18:- Formulation of Batch C1-C8

Formulation ingredients	TRIAL BATCHES							
	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8
Clonazepam	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Lactose monohydrate	35.5	31.5	29.5	25.5	24	24	21	19
Maize starch	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	32
Pregelatinised starch	10	14	16	20	20	20	20	20
Water	qs	qs	qs	qs	qs	qs	qs	qs
MCC101	10	10	10	10	10	10	13	13
Iron oxide red	1	1	1	1	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Talc	2	2	2	2	3	3	3	3
Mg,staerate	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Total	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90

3.7 Comparative Dissolution profile of Desvenlafaxine succinate of batch DC8:D8+C6

Table 19:- comparative Dissolution profile of Desvenlafaxine succinate of batch DC8:D8+C6

Time in hours	Market	Batch
0.5	2.3	3.7
1	11.5	12.5
2	20.5	22.1
4	34.5	36.2
6	42	43.5
8	58.7	60.1
12	69.8	72.9
16	81.4	81.9
20	93.7	92.4
24	102	101

Graph 9: comparative Dissolution profile of Desvenlafaxine succinate of batch DC8:D8+C6 with market sample

3.8 Comparative Dissolution profile of Clonazepam of batch DC8:D8+C6

Table 20:- comparative Dissolution profile of Clonazepam of batch DC8:D8+C6 with market sample

Time in Minutes	Marketed sample	DC8:D8+C6
5	22	24.1
10	44	46.5
15	68	67.2
30	89	88.1
45	92	92.3
60	100	99.7

Graph 10: comparative Dissolution profile of Clonazepam of batch DC8:D8+C6 with market sample

3.9 Graph dissolution profile of same initial 3 months For Desvenlafaxine succinate and Clonazepam

4. CONCLUSION

The study was undertaken with an aim to formulate develop and evaluation of Desvenlafaxine succinate sustained release using different polymers as release retarding agent and clonazepam immediate release layer using different types Super disintegrants. Pre formulation study of Desvenlafaxine succinate and Clonazepam was done initially and results directed for the further course of formulation. Based on preformulation studies different batches were prepared using selected excipients. Granules were evaluated for tests LOD. Bulk density, Tapped density, Compressibility index, Hausner ratio before being punches as tablets. Tablets were tested for weight variations, thickness, hardness, friability as per official procedure.

Dissolution was carried out in 0.9 N NaCl for Desvenlafaxine succinate and water in Clonazepam. Based on dissolution tests and F-2 values in 0.9 N NaCl and water release medium, it was concluded that Batch number DC8:D8+C6 mostly match with their respective innovator individual market tablet

5. REFERENCES

- Andrade, C. (2015). Sustained-release, extended-release, and other time-release formulations in neuropsychiatry. *The Journal of clinical psychiatry*, 76(8), 20558.
- Kiran, B., Rao, P. S., Babu, G. R., & Kumari, M. V. (2015). BILAYER TABLETS-A REVIEW. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical, Chemical & Biological Sciences*, 5(3).
- Franek, F., Jarlfors, A., Larsen, F., Holm, P., & Steffansen, B. (2015). In vitro solubility, dissolution and permeability studies combined with semi-mechanistic modeling to investigate the intestinal absorption of desvenlafaxine from an immediate-and extended release formulation. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 77, 303
- Olivier, B. (2015). Serotonin: a never-ending story. *European journal of pharmacology*, 753, 2-18.
- Brigo, F., & Lattanzi, S. (2022). Anti-convulsant agents: benzodiazepines (clobazam, clonazepam, diazepam, lorazepam, midazolam). In *NeuroPsychopharmacotherapy* (pp. 3753-3760). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Mahmood, T., Sarfraz, R. M., Ismail, A., Ali, M., & Khan, A. R. (2023). Pharmaceutical methods for enhancing the dissolution of poorly water-soluble drugs. *ASSAY and Drug Development Technologies*, 21(2), 65-79.
- Segall, A. I. (2019). Preformulation: The use of FTIR in compatibility studies.
- Savva, M. (2019). *Pharmaceutical Calculations* (pp. 275-284). Cham, Switzerland: Springer International Publishing.
- Razavi, S. M., Scicolone, J., Snee, R. D., Kumar, A., Bertels, J., Cappuyns, P., & Muzzio, F. (2020). Prediction of tablet weight variability in continuous manufacturing. *International journal of pharmaceutics*, 575, 118727.
- Osei-Yeboah, F., & Sun, C. C. (2015). Validation and applications of an expedited tablet friability method. *International journal of pharmaceutics*, 484(1-2), 146-155.
- Leshe, S. (2015). Practical Analytical chemistry.
- Alasabashi, M. (2021). *Analysis of Psychotropic Medicines Olanzapine, Clorazepate, Escitalopram Mixture Using Thin-Layer and High-Performance Liquid Chromatography Methods* (Master's thesis, Lithuanian University of Health Sciences (Lithuania)).